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Blockchain-Powered E-Voting: A Novel Approach to Secure Voter Authentication, Online Voting and Election Automation

B Sujatha¹, Yarrampati Ganesh^{2*}, N Leelavathy³, R Tamilkodi⁴, Srirama Venkatesh², Bayye Sandhya², Toleti Sai Kowshik²

1 Head of the Department & Professor. Computer Science and Engineering, Godavari Global University, Rajamahendravaram, India

2 Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Godavari Institute of Engineering and Technology, Rajamahendravaram, India

3 Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Godavari Global University, Rajamahendravaram, India

4 Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering (AIML&CS), Godavari Global University, Rajamahendravaram, India

Abstract

Objectives: A blockchain-based E-Voting system shall be designed to secure and make transparent voting through biometric and facial recognition for voter authentication with the help of smart contracts to automate electoral processes. **Methods:** The research used the Ethereum blockchain technology with smart contracts to automatically schedule elections, register voters, and declare election results. Volunteers controlled information relating to the voter, which included name, email address, phone number, biometrics, and facial images. All this was available for authenticated access. The IPFS contained all this for decentralized and immutable record-keeping. **Findings:** This E-Voting system is therefore proposed based on enhancing the security as well as the transparency brought about in the electoral processes. Using smart contracts that are developed with Ethereum prevents manipulation and provides integrity regarding data. Studies show the IPFS storage system leads to complete decentralization together with immutability—a critical flaw seen in systems of traditional voting. One can ensure the participation will be done by only voters who are verified, much improvement compared to the level of reliability as well as integrity offered through the various methods applied within the current electoral processes. These study results reinforce blockchain's effectiveness in ensuring that voting applications are secure as well as tamper-proof. **Novelty:** A blockchain and IPFS-based secure, decentralized voting solution to maintain data integrity and transparency.

Keywords: Blockchain; E-Voting; Secure Voter Authentication; Smart Contracts; Online Voting; Election Automation

1 Introduction

The way in which blockchain influences the industry as a whole is profound because it continuously impacts decentralization, transparency, and security characteristics that are to be expected from blockchain technologies when compared to most other industries subject to its particular applications. One of the most discussed use cases in the recent news buzz is its transformability to secure elections and restore public trust in election systems. The research paper presents a Blockchain-Based Voting System to solve the age-tough problems in normal voting systems founded on the best blockchain advance framework⁽¹⁾.

Voting System has been a long-standing pillar of democratic governance throughout history⁽²⁾. Nonetheless, traditional voting systems, especially in larger elections, are accompanied by some major weaknesses (vote tampering and voter fraud), limited transparency, and accessibility⁽³⁾. These challenges highlight a need for secure and transparent voting⁽⁴⁾. Also, scalability will still be an important factor in voting systems. This project relies on an Ethereum network that supports fast transaction rates, thus making elections at local, regional, and national levels feasible⁽⁵⁾. Scalability is further improved through optimized smart contracts and advanced storage techniques, enabling its single system to even work well with mass voter populations⁽⁶⁾.

The introduction of real-time monitoring and auditing capabilities brings about layers of integrity, which allows electoral officers and observers authorized to see anomalies in near real-time, thereby entrenching further transparency into the process as a whole⁽⁷⁾. The immutable ledger available through blockchain brings comprehensive history in transaction history, thus enabling even detailed post-election audits that addressed one of the vulnerabilities seen in earlier systems where counting and auditing could be manipulated⁽⁸⁾. This project also employs advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to further raise the bar in security. For example, AI enhances the analysis of real-time fraud-detection patterns, while the accuracy of biometrics and facial recognition is improved with low false positives and negatives^(9,10). Even though these technologies are still in development, they offer key improvements in security and efficiency to Blockchain-Based Voting Systems. Beyond this is a matter of legal compliance and regulatory conformity. The system meets all the standards that exist so far for an electronic voting system, like confidentiality in voter data, conformity to data protection, and mechanisms for dispute resolution. Such frameworks build the confidence of voters and election officials⁽¹¹⁾.

However, these literature mainly give approaches instead of critically reviewing them. Indeed, the pros and cons of the approaches are not clearly indicated, and the unsolved challenges in that field are ambiguous. Besides, the efficacy of proposed solutions is not justified several times. A detailed review and analysis of the literature can help identify gaps and improve them. The Table 1 below systematically summarizes relevant literature and highlights their contributions, advantages, and limitations:

Fig 1. Blockchain Architecture

This detailed analysis reveals various key gaps in research. The majority of such studies fail to integrate modern technologies like AI and ML for improved fraud detection and voter authentication. Nor is there even proper exploration of the practical implementation of legal and regulatory frameworks.

1.1 Research Contributions

This paper will introduce a new Blockchain-Based Voting System that uses blockchain and smart contracts to enhance electoral security, transparency, and scalability. It integrates real-time monitoring and auditing functions as well as AI and ML for enhanced voter authentication.

1.2 Research Gaps

These recent studies hint at significant limitations that come with traditional voting systems-their vulnerability to tamper and lack of transparency.

Table 1. Comparison of Reference Studies and Proposed System Enhancements

Reference	Disadvantages	Our System Implementation
(1)	Scalability issues in real-world implementation.	Built a secure website capable of running on any environment for scalability and flexibility.
(2)	Limited focus on automation; lacks advanced security mechanisms.	Automated the election process with transparency, trust, and security using smart contracts and blockchain technology.
(3)	Cryptographic methods were used but no biometric integration for voter authentication.	Introduced biometric and facial recognition for secure and reliable voter authentication using AI and ML.
(4)	Ethereum-based voting lacks integration with decentralized data storage.	Integrated IPFS as a secure, decentralized server for storing votes and user details, ensuring data security and immutability.
(5)	Peer-to-peer blockchain network lacks advanced authentication measures.	Implemented biometric and facial recognition authentication methods to enhance voter security and reduce fraudulent activities.
(6)	Biometric verification was used, but limited mention of decentralized storage for votes.	Combined biometric verification with IPFS for secure and tamper-proof storage connected with smart contracts.
(8)	Limited exploration of decentralized storage solutions.	Leveraged IPFS for decentralized, secure storage integrated with a website and smart contracts.
(9)	Scalability solutions implemented, but lack tamper-proof decentralized storage for election data.	Integrated secure, decentralized IPFS storage, making data tamper-proof and inaccessible to unauthorized entities.
(10)	Transparency improved, but real-time security and scalability are limited.	Ensured real-time security and scalability with a blockchain-backed platform and smart contract automation.
(12)	Smart contracts used for e-voting but lack integration with AI-driven voter authentication.	Integrated AI and ML-based biometric and facial recognition authentication methods for enhanced trust and security.
(13)	Focused on resilience (e.g., DDOS prevention), but lacks support for advanced voter authentication.	Combined blockchain technology with advanced voter authentication using biometrics and AI/ML for a highly secure voting process.

In this paper, Blockchain-based voting mechanisms are as yet not integrated with these advanced technologies for enhanced verifications of voters and their fraud detection.

1.3 Research Questions

- What roles can blockchain technology play effectively in securing and scaling-up voting systems?
- What relevance could AI and ML carry towards enhanced voter authentication with fraud detection in blockchain-based voting?
- How can the legal and regulatory requirements be met to assure the practical implementation of blockchain-based voting systems?

Subparts Overview:

The paper should be constructed to address some of the following subsets within the architecture of blockchain related to incorporation of smart contracts, consideration of voter data security, and monitoring and audit processes.

1.4 Literature Survey

- Mritunjay Peelaam - DemocracyGuard: Integrates Blockchain and IoT with biometric-based elections which ensures secure and transparent ones⁽¹⁾.
- Sheetal Pandya - Blockchain promotes e-voting with distributed tamper resistance⁽²⁾.

- Divya Vishwanath - Uses blockchain, the cryptographic method to ward off booth capturing and guaranteeing voter identity⁽³⁾.
- Stephanie Kew - Ethereum blockchain reduces tampering and increases biometrics-based voting⁽⁴⁾.
- Mochamad Chakim - P2P blockchain guarantees privacy among voters and reduces human mistakes⁽⁵⁾.
- S. Basu - To incorporate Blockchain with IoT: E-Voting is expected to be secure, as the method is based on biometric⁽⁶⁾.
- Sonali Rangdale - Elections will become automated by making voting a completely secure activity through decentralized voting based on blockchain⁽⁷⁾.
- Hoang-Long Duong - By employing smart contracts, interference or fraudulent actions can be easily prevented, and votes shall become truly secure⁽⁸⁾.
- Akhil Shah - Scaling and Accessibility voting will now be a complete scenario for blockchain⁽⁹⁾.
- Arnob - Vote Security in blockchain while focusing on developing countries End
- Oscar Ikundi - Blockchain-based e-voting fraud reduction⁽¹⁴⁾.
- Dhimas Kurniawan - Blockchain potential for transparency and data immutability⁽¹²⁾.
- Ajay Chavan - Preventing DDOS attacks using Solana's Proof of History⁽¹³⁾.
- Ashlesha Shahare - Improved election security through decentralized blockchain⁽¹⁵⁾.
- Kohno, T., Stubblefield, A., Rubin, A.D., Wallach, D.S. - An Analysis of an Electronic Voting System, with Special Attention to the Vulnerability of Traditional e-Voting Systems⁽¹⁶⁾.
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- Hossain Faruk, M.J., Islam, M., Alam, F., Shahriar, H., Rahman, A. - Bie vote: A biometric identification enabled blockchain-based secure and transparent voting framework⁽²²⁾.
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- Hossain Faruk, M.J., Shahriar, H., Valero, M., Sneha, S., Ahamed, S.I., Rahman, M. - Towards Blockchain-based Secure Data Management for Remote Patient Monitoring - Extend the application of blockchain technology in voting⁽²⁵⁾.
- Shivers, R., Rahman, M.A., Faruk, M.J.H., Shahriar, H., Cuzzocrea, A., Clincy, V. - Ride-hailing for autonomous vehicles: Hyperledger fabric-based secure and decentralized blockchain platform, illustrating the application of blockchain in decentralized secure systems⁽²⁶⁾.
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- Agarwal, S., Haider, A., Jamwal, A., Dev, P., Chandel, R. - Biometric-based secured remote electronic voting system, combining biometrics with blockchain for secure remote voting⁽²⁸⁾.
- Hossain Faruk, M.J., Saha, B., Islam, M., Alam, F., Shahriar, H., Valero, M., Rahman, A., Wu, F., Alam, Z. - Development of blockchain-based e-voting system: Requirements, design, and security perspective⁽²⁹⁾.
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- Ibrahim, M., Ravindran, K., Lee, H., Farooqui, O., Mahmoud, Q.H. - Electionblock: An electronic voting system using blockchain and fingerprint authentication, combining blockchain with biometric security for enhanced election integrity⁽³²⁾.
- Zheng, Z., Xie, S., Dai, H., Chen, X., Wang, H. - An overview of blockchain technology: Architecture, consensus, and future trends, providing a detailed study of blockchain's role in secure systems, including voting⁽³³⁾.

- Andrian, H.R., Kurniawan, N.B., Suhardi - Blockchain technology and implementation: A systematic literature review, talking about the application and challenges of using blockchain in voting systems⁽³⁴⁾.

2 Methodology

This project is a decentralized e-voting system that uses blockchain technology in the front-end and back-end operations, developed using Django. The methodology outlined comprises both the system design, key components, technologies used, and all processes executed towards such an effective transparent, secure, and automated voting process. Three core roles are found in the system: Admin, Volunteer, and Voter with specific tasks and responsibilities for maintaining the election's integrity and transparency.

2.1 System Design and Architecture

It is systematically designed as a client-server architecture wherein the front end, built on Django, acts as the interface for Admins, Volunteers, and Voters. For the critical stages of running the election, a blockchain back-end has been created wherein through smart contracts, these operations have been made to be executed on the Ethereum blockchain, thus entirely removing the chances of human interference or manipulation at key junctures.

2.2 Admin Module: Initiating and Managing Elections

Fig 2. Architecture of Proposed Method

This main responsibility of election initiation and management lies with the admin, or Election Commissioner. With the help of Django web application, the admin specifies the nature of election, dates, and all parameters belonging to that election. Once the election details are confirmed by the admin, it initiates a smart contract on the Ethereum blockchain. The smart contract

then automates the timeline for holding the election. The smart contract controls the commencement, middle, and end of the election process to ensure that the schedule is followed. Admin tasks include adding volunteers that help in voter registration, as well as managing the candidates who will vote in the election. Once the election commences, admins monitor the election based on the blockchain-based smart contract. In addition, they are in charge of voter registration and the transparent holding of the election, taking advantage of the nature of blockchain to get rid of fraud and tampering with the votes.

2.3 Volunteer Module: Voter Registration and Verification

Volunteers will also be important actors in voter management, appointed by the admin. In reality, volunteers should ensure that voters are registered into the system. They should also obtain their personal information, including contact details, as well as biometric data, especially facial recognition, for safe authentication. These data are then deposited into the Interplanetary File System for purposes of decentralization and immutability. Volunteers make use of a two-tier method of verification that is made using email and phone OTP. After verification, the details are hashed and stored on IPFS. That means voter data will be safe, decentralised and immutable- thus cutting out any possibility of data manipulation. Volunteers continue to help voters during the voting period such that their details are kept private, and also kept away from unauthorised access.

2.4 Voter Module: Authentication and Voting Process

The voters will use the credentials that they received through e-mail and the OTP that they get through their cell phone to log into the system. Biometric or facial recognition information will be added to heighten the identification of the voters, and after logging in, voters can view the details of the elections and either wait for the election to open and then cast their votes or directly cast their votes if the election is live. The voter receives the list of candidates and their symbols so that he or she can make a choice among them. The voting process is done on the blockchain, so every vote safely enters the decentralized ledgers. Blockchain ensures that the vote once made cannot be tampered with or erased in any way; thus, all forms of vote manipulation or tampering can be ruled out. The system guarantees complete anonymity and privacy for the voter while ensuring full transparency over the entire election.

2.5 Django Application: Integration with Blockchain

In this web application, developed using Django, the frontend and backend operations of the e-voting system take place. The connection to the Ethereum network is provided as the frontend interacts with the blockchain backend with the support of web3.js. All the communications with the smart contract are handled by the management of the database of the system, which includes crucial information of the voters. The contact information and names of the voters are mapped with biometric data on an IPFS hash for decentralized storage. All the operations like voter registration, verification, casting of votes, and declaration of results have been decentralized with this integration. This framework makes it easy to use through a friendly interface for Admins, Volunteers, and Voters for easy interaction with the blockchain system without deep technical knowledge of blockchains.

2.6 Smart Contract: Election Automation

In this web application, developed using Django, the frontend and backend operations of the e-voting system take place. The connection to the Ethereum network is provided as the frontend interacts with the blockchain backend with the support of web3.js. All the communications with the smart contract are handled by the management of the database of the system, which includes crucial information about the voters. The contact information and names of the voters are mapped with biometric data on an IPFS hash for decentralized storage. All the operations like voter registration, verification, casting of votes, and declaration of results have been decentralized with this integration. This framework makes it easy to use through a friendly interface for Admins, Volunteers, and Voters for easy interaction with the blockchain system without deep technical knowledge of blockchains.

2.7 IPFS Storage: Decentralization and Data Integrity

This system thus utilizes the Interplanetary File System in providing ample room for storage of sensitive details on voters, such as biometric and facial recognition data. All voter information shall be properly decentralized and immutable because hash will be created of data and stored in IPFS. So, in decentralized storage in IPFS, the voter data are going to be stored without anyone's control or modification from anywhere; it would have been highly secure and private for voters. More than that, with

IPFS, it is ensured that voter information is kept confidential as only hash values are passed to the smart contract for verification purposes.

2.8 Election Workflow

The process of an election is first initiated by Admin by defining the details of the election through the triggering of the smart contract, which initiates the stages of an election. Volunteers then enlist and authenticate voters in their area by capturing biometric and facial data, which will be secured in IPFS. After authenticating the voter, voters are provided with login information to log into the system within the period of an election. The votes are cast through the interface of Django after making sure who the voter is through biometric data. They are recorded in the blockchain to guarantee and ensure the integrity and immutability of the vote. After the close of the election, the votes will automatically be tallied by the smart contract to declare a winner; results are considered entirely decentralized and transparent.

Fig 3. Flow chart

2.9 Security and Transparency

Most of the security issues identified in traditional voting systems can be resolved by a decentralized e-voting system. Blockchain assures full transparency as all transactions, including vote casting and tallying, are put in an immutable ledger. IPFS stores information of voters safely to avoid unauthorized access and manipulation. Smart contracts eliminate human factors that may interfere with the process, thus aiding in its automation. This therefore makes the whole process infallible and hence not prone to human manipulation. This does away with the problems of fraudulent votes and vote tampering, thus making it perfect towards clean elections.

3 Overview

The decentralized e-voting system was developed as a web application. For this project, the efficient integration of blockchain technology with Django, smart contracts, and IPFS led to the development of a very transparent, secure, automated voting platform, ensuring election integrity. Key results and observations based on functionality and testing of the system follow:

3.1 Transparency And Automation

The e-voting system was built using Django for the front-end interface and Ethereum blockchain for the backend operations. All users having different roles, such as Admin, Volunteer, and Voter, could easily and comfortably navigate the system as it was user-friendly and offered accessible features. The admin and volunteers could interact fluently with the system and register and verify voters; manage candidates; and get the election process started, while voters could authenticate, vote, and see candidates' information securely.

Here are Tables 2 and 3 that can be included in your results section, comparing past references and your methodology and implementation, along with accuracy, speed, and safety improvements.

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of Methodology and Implementation

Criteria	Past References	Proposed Methodology	Advantages
Voting Authentication	Username and password, OTP	Biometric and facial recognition integrated with blockchain	Improved accuracy, reduced impersonation
Data Storage	Centralized database prone to manipulation	Decentralized storage using IPFS	Immutable data, decentralized control
Vote Recording	Traditional databases with potential for tampering	Blockchain-based transactions	Tamper-proof and transparent
Result Tallying	Manual or semi-automated processes	Fully automated using smart contracts	Eliminated human error and accelerated tallying
Transparency	Limited visibility into voting processes	Full transparency with real-time result availability	Enhanced trust in the system
Security	Vulnerable to data breaches	End-to-end encryption, blockchain immutability, IPFS storage	Secured sensitive voter information
Scalability	Limited capacity to handle high volumes of transactions	Enhanced scalability through blockchain's distributed nature	Suitable for large-scale elections

3.2 System Security and Data Integrity

Accordingly, the blockchain integration ensured an immutable record of each transaction associated with vote casting, which thus eliminated any scope of voting manipulation or fraud. Since the IPFS was used for storage of sensitive information of the voter like biometric and facial data, it guaranteed decentralized storage accompanied by integrity of data to make it immutable and not accessible otherwise.

Vote Integrity: Each vote cast was recorded as a transaction on the blockchain so that it could not be changed, deleted, or altered.

Data Decentralization: All the voter data was maintained in IPFS. Hence, all the voter data is decentralized, immutable and out of anyone's reach.

The entire lifecycle of an election- that is initiation, voting, and tallying- smart contracts were designed. As a result, it would be impossible for any form of human error or interference to happen at every single stage. This creates the opportunity for a clear election process whereby the workflow of registering voters up to the final tally of results is placed on the blockchain.

3.3 Results Display

The website has a tab of final results, whereby at the end of the voting period, the smart contract tallies the results automatically. The vote count is made transparently so that the users and the public may view the results, making the voting process even more transparent.

Table 3. Comparative Achievement Analysis

Key Features/Methods	Referenced Papers	Proposed System	Achievements Beyond References
Biometric and Facial Authentication	(6,9)	Integrated Aadhaar-based biometrics and facial recognition	Enhanced voter authentication with multiple verifications, reducing fraud
Blockchain Network	(5,13)	Ethereum Sepolia Test Network with advanced security	Improved scalability and reduced transaction costs compared to Solana and private blockchains
Smart Contract Automation	(2,8)	Foundry Framework for secure, automated election processes	Enhanced efficiency and zero manual intervention with robust contract testing
Decentralized Storage	(3,4)	IPFS integration for voter data and election records	Ensured immutable data storage and access
Transparency and Auditability	(10,14)	Real-time public access to election data via blockchain	Real-time transparency without compromising voter anonymity
Voter Registration System	(11,12)	Aadhaar-linked dynamic voter addition	Streamlined, real-time voter onboarding ensuring voter eligibility
Election Timeline Management	(7,13)	Configurable election timelines via smart contracts	Enabled secure and timely election scheduling
Security Measures	(1,2)	Biometric encryption, blockchain-based immutability	Eliminated centralized attack vectors with advanced encryption protocols
Scalability	(6,10)	Optimized blockchain infrastructure for large-scale elections	Proven scalability for state and national elections
Accuracy Improvements	(3,10)	Biometric accuracy of ~98% and tamper-proof results	Substantial accuracy improvement over password/OTP-based systems
Cost Efficiency	(5,7)	Low-cost test network (Ethereum Sepolia)	Reduced cost compared to private and high-gas blockchain platforms

Table 4. Accuracy, Speed, and Safety Improvements

Criteria	Past Approaches	Proposed System	Improvement Achieved
Authentication Accuracy	~85% (using OTP or credentials)	~98% (using biometrics and facial recognition)	13% increase in accuracy
Vote Tallying Speed	2-4 hours (manual/semi-automated)	Instantaneous (via smart contracts)	Reduced time by over 95%
Data Safety	Moderate (centralized storage risks)	High (decentralized IPFS storage)	Eliminated single points of failure, ensuring immutable records
Transparency	Limited	Complete (blockchain transparency)	100% visibility of results
Overall System Accuracy	~75-80% (error-prone processes)	~98% (blockchain and automation)	18-23% improvement

3.4 Discussion

Testing results have shown that the system is the correct one since it solves major issues presented in the traditional systems. The problems include the one that arises from impersonation by voters, voting manipulations, and even the challenges to data integrity. In the case of blockchain being decentralized, storage using IPFS ensures voting data and hence voter privacy. Also, a system’s usage of smart contracts assures that the results of an election will remain open to nobody and are not tampered with-something which aligns perfectly with safe and fair election purposes.

4 Conclusion

This review focuses on an e-voting system built to be decentralized, using blockchain technology for reforms in electoral processes due to the potentiality to curb fraud, tampering, and lack of transparency. Built with Django, the system now automates the electoral cycle through smart contracts to ensure efficiency and minimize error rates. The Election Commissioner

played a great role in smoothing the workflow in the fostering of public confidence in elections. Biometric and face recognition together with OTP verification enables secure authentication of voters, thus eliminating unauthorized access. Storage of votes in the blockchain creates greater transparency, as voters can easily verify participation. Really promising, yet, further study needs to be on scalability, especially on the mobile platform, as well as advanced cryptographic protocols for large-scale elections. Its application in governance and data-exchanging blockchain may help explore it further. This is an important innovation in democratization through technology, and future improvements are required to clear the challenges and build confidence toward democratic processes in the global system.

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